

Thinking Global Labour History: Problems and Prospects

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ABSTRACT

Paradigmatically Global Labor History distinguishes itself from the earlier labor histories and posits a new theoretical vision before the historians of global labor. Tight compartmentalization and classification of the historical reality into local, regional, national and or even world history signify the preclusion of multifarious trans-border transactions. So, the rationale for global history is also an appeal to overcome such divisions and to reach at a more complete perception of the interactions and connections, which made the modern world what it is today. Global Labor History is present in the form of the development of research agenda given the vast diversity in working class formations and rise and growth of class culture in varied nations across the globe, Finally, the fast-changing economic landscape as evident in the rise of the gig economy impact the laborers and their livelihoods globally.

Key words: Global Labor History, Globe, Modern World, Diversity.

Introduction

The Global Labor History claims to be as an important academic discipline in the last two decades. Here the contributions of Marcel van der Linden, a significant global labor historian and influencer of the discipline ‘Global Labor History’, and the International Institute of Social History (IISH) established in 1935 in Amsterdam are particularly remarkable. It, however, in its trajectory of progress, encounters certain challenges, which are both methodologically and theoretically crucial. Overcoming these challenges, the Global Labor History gets strengthened and consolidated as an important discipline with new and robust global perspective with implications for labor history across the globe.

As E. H. Carr declares in his seminal work *What is History?* that history is not imagination, but an “interpretation”¹, which is firmly based on facts. He further asserts that History is “...a continuous process of interaction between the historian and his facts, an unending dialogue between the present and the past.”² Till recent years, history in most areas is limited to national history. The nation-state becomes the fundamental unit of historical research. Writing about nation-state has become routine historical exercise. To go even further, it is almost a standard approach to confine the historical lens to the very minute aspects of the society, economy, polity, culture, religion, science, and technology of the nation-state.

Understanding Contours of World History

Interestingly, in the recent years or more particularly in the last three decades, the world history began to grow popular and “... has become one of the fastest growing areas of teaching.”³ Therefore, understandably, the question that needs to be elucidated is ‘What exactly is world history?’⁴ Jerry Bentley, the To him, “Thus, world history represents (among other things, no doubt) a dialogue between the past and the present (here echoing the perception of E.H. Carr on ‘*what is history?*’), in that it seeks to establish a historical context for the integrated and interdependent world of modern times.”⁵ William H. McNeill, one of the foremost historians, who wrote path breaking works on the concept of the World History⁶

¹ E.H. Carr, *What is History?*, Penguin Books, 1964, pp. 12-13; Note: “The writing of history is an interpretive act, and it relies upon the reading of complex Bloomsbury Publishing, 2018, p. 20.

asserts that “Suffice it to say, therefore, that civilizations do seem real to me, and have in fact united many millions of human beings across millions of square miles and many centuries in significant ways.”⁷ And when “diverse civilizations begin to impinge on one another more and more often... the autonomy and independence of the separate civilizations begin to shrink, and a new cosmopolitan entity, what Wallerstein calls a world system...the emergence of the ecumenical world system within which we live today.”⁸ In Mc Neill’s concept of World History, the trans-civilizational encounters, trading contacts, exchange of ideas, transmission of knowledge of science and technologies and interactions among peoples of varied cultures over the centuries contribute to the emergence of a world system.⁹ There were several scholars writing on the varied aspects and processes shaping the world.¹⁰ The history of these processes is the history of the world. Historians exploring these historical processes nationally are also participating in unravelling the larger historical processes of the World. As C.A. Bayly declares that “All historians are world historians now, though many have not yet realized it.”¹¹ So, every history is local, but all history is thus global.

Rise and Rage of Global History

Global history broadly implies a form of historical analysis in which events and processes are placed in global contexts. Hitherto the writing of history in various countries is mostly equated with the writing of national histories. Generations of students were introduced to the writing and study of national histories. Narrating a nation’s past has been the seminal task of a historian. The cross-border intersections, exchanges, parallels, and entanglements are mostly ignored or underplayed. Global history is the history of the networked and globalized world. It is aptly observed that “... the world we live in has come into its own as an integrated globe...Global integration is a fact; now part of the historical record...”¹²

² *Ibid*, p. 30.

³ Michael Geyer and Charles Bright, ‘World History in a Global Age’, *The American Historical Review*, Oct, 1995, Vol. 100, No. 4 (Oct., 1995), p. 1037.

⁴ Bruce Mazlish, ‘Comparing Global History to World History’, *The Journal of Interdisciplinary History*, Winter, 1998, Vol. 28, No. 3 (Winter, 1998), p. 385.

⁵ Jerry H. Bentley, Review of Mazlish, Bruce; Buultjens, Ralph, *Conceptualizing Global History*. H-World, H-Net Reviews, August 1995. URL: <http://www.h-net.org/reviews/showrev.php?id=137>

⁶ William H. McNeill, *The Rise of the West: A History of the Human Community*, University of Chicago Press,

There is, however, certain degree of ‘obfuscation’ in perception of the difference between world history and global history. Apart from etymological meaning, the distinction between them is explained with reference to the historical processes where the role of the phenomenon of globalization is central. Therefore, this question has been broadly answered:

The starting point for global history lies in the following basic facts of our time (although others could be added): our thrust into space, imposing upon us an increasing sense of being in one world- “Spaceship Earth”-as seen from outside the earth’s atmosphere; satellites in outer space that link the peoples of the earth in an unprecedented fashion; nuclear threats in the form of either weapons or utility plants, showing how the territorial state can no longer adequately protect its citizens from either military or ecologically related “invasions”; environmental problems that refuse to conform to lines drawn on a map; and multinational corporations that increasingly dominate our economic lives.¹³

A quick glance at the some of the world changing events and processes would point to the remarkable ways in which the modern world is connected. To mention some of the developments from the last decades of the nineteenth century to the last decade of the twentieth century, politically significant are the decline of the major empires such as Habsburg empire, Ramanov dynasty, the Qing dynasty, journalists around the globe communicating news through telegraph cable instantaneously that integrated the world much faster. The other significant developments that greatly fashioned the modern world are the World War I and its aftermath, the global economic depression in 1930s resulting in the rise of ideologies such as the fascist, totalitarian, and nationalist ideologies, and the starting of World War II and its aftermath, the decolonization that followed and the rise of new nations. The rise of the Cold War and its demise with the disintegrations of the Soviet Union are yet other remarkable events that culminated in redesigning the political and economic relations internationally. Of course, the role of the League of Nations and the United Nations in the preservation of international order and security must not be missed.¹⁴ As it has been aptly

1963, also *Plagues and Peoples*, Anchor Books, Doubleday New York, 1976.

⁷ William H. McNeill, ‘The Rise of the West after Twenty-Five Years’, *Journal of World History*, Vol.1, No. 1

⁸ *Ibid.*, pp. 9-10; See also Immanuel Wallerstein, *The Modern World-System*, 3 vols. (New York, 1974–1988)

⁹ See William H. McNeill, ‘The Changing Shape of World History’, *History and Theory*, May 1995, Vol. 34, No.2, Theme Issue 34: World Historians and Their Critics (May 1995) pp. 8-26.

observed that International trade brought poorer countries into a global economy, significantly boosting living standards.”¹⁵

Thus “The last decades of the twentieth century saw the most remarkable transformation of the human condition for the better than any time in recorded history.”¹⁶ It was possible because of the “...creation of a network of global institutions”¹⁷ which coordinated the actions of the nation states to cope with problems that “transcend” which has both good and bad repercussions for modern world. Global history (global historian) deals with the events and the processes such as the “...four dominant global experiences in the twentieth century: (1) economic development and technological progress; (2) global conflicts (World War I, World War II, and the Cold War; (3) global order and institutional building; and (4) social revolutions (such as anticolonialism, socialism, nationalism, justice, and women’s empowerment).”¹⁸ As Michael J. Green observed suggestively that “The bottom-line lesson is that no nation-state is immune from global history or absolved of responsibility for understanding its impact as each state defines its role in a new century.”¹⁹ As Diego Olstein articulates that it is necessary to have the four thinking strategies to have global perspectives. These four strategies for thinking history globally are: comparing, connecting, conceptualizing, and contextualizing.²⁰

Thinking Global Labor History

Just as the rise of Global History, the Global Labor History too began to emerge as a significant field of research in the last decade of the twentieth century²¹

¹⁰ Note: See for instance the scholars namely Fernand Braudel, Immanuel Wallerstein and Abu-Lughod, who demonstrated through their works the interconnectedness of the World.

¹¹ C.A. Bayly, *The Birth of the Modern World, 1780-1914: Global Connections and Comparisons*, Blackwell Publishing, Malden, MA, 2004, p. 469.

¹² Michael Geyer and Charles Bright, *op. cit*

¹³ Cited in Bruce Mazlish, *op.cit.*, p. 390.

¹⁴ Note: These ideas are collected from John J. Hamre’s Foreword to Michael J. Green and Nicholas Szechenyi (ed), *A Global History of the Twentieth Century-Legacies and Lessons from Six National Perspectives*, CSIS, Rowman and Littlefield, New York, 2017, p.p. vi- xiv.

¹⁵ *Ibid*, p. ix.

¹⁶ *Ibid*.

¹⁷ *Ibid*.

¹⁸ *Ibid*, p. 3.

and the first decades of the twenty first century.²² One Scholar and the Research institute greatly credited with and immensely involved in promoting the discipline of the Global Labor History are Marcel van der Linden and the International Institute of Social History (IISH).²³ Dorothy Sue Cobble aptly calls van der Linden as ‘...one of the most influential proponents of “global labor history...”²⁴ for advocating and making his contributions to the “global turn” in labor history. Peter Winn writes that “Marcel van der Linden, as a historian, promoter, and organizer, has played a leading role in its advances.”²⁵ Prasannan Parthasarathi, an eminent scholar of economic history, states that the global labor history, to Marcel van der Linden, is a “distinctive ‘field of research’ just like ‘art history or linguistics’”. He goes on to explain that van der Linden considers it as ‘a subset of the larger field of global history’ He mentions that ‘according to van der Linden, the practice of global labor history is “in the first instance a question of mentality” demanding historians “be bold in their inquiry, and dare to venture outside their familiar terrain.”²⁶ In other words, what van der Linden, meant here was that the historians working on labor must attempt to cross the national and disciplinary boundaries in their endeavour to probe historical aspects of different forms of free or unfree labor and “...especially for the study of their interconnections... as well as of the economic, political, social, and cultural networks, institutions and media which played a role in it.”²⁷

It is axiomatic that the Global Labor History is essentially concerned with “interconnections”. Therefore, it is to be noted that “...It is only within a global framework that the many connections and mutual influences can be contained and understood.”²⁸ Like the Global History, Global Labor History too urges for interrogation of historical aspects locally, nationally, and establishing comparisons and connections between them globally. Marcel van der Linden, while explaining the mission of the ‘Global Labour History Network’ (GLHN),

¹⁹ *Ibid*, p. 11.

²⁰ Diego Olstein, *Thinking History Globally*, Palgrave Macmillan, New York, 2015, pp. 6-7.

²¹ Peter Winn, ‘Global Labor History: The Future of the Field?’, *International Labor and Working-Class History*, Fall 2012, No. 82, Fortieth Anniversary Issue (Fall 2012), p. 86.

²² Marcel van der Linden, ‘Global Labour History: Two Essays’, *V. V. Giri National Labour Institute*, New Delhi, p. v.; also see Dorothy Sue Cobble, ‘The Promise and Peril of the New Global Labor History’, *International Labor and Working-Class History*, Fall 2012, No. 82, Fortieth Anniversary Issue (Fall 2012), p. 99.

²³ <https://iisg.amsterdam/en/about/history/detailed-history-iish>,
<https://iisg.amsterdam/en/blog/hub-global-labour-conflicts>

²⁴ Dorothy Sue Cobble, *op.cit.*, p. 99.

which was founded in June 2015 in Barcelona, refers to what Global Labour History would essentially deal with. He writes thus:

“...We are interested in paid and unpaid, free and unfree, productive and reproductive labour, in all areas of the globe and without temporal limitation. While our mandate includes modern rural and industrial workers such as miners, factory operatives, agricultural workers and dockers, it welcomes also those studying soldiers, domestic servants, sex workers, and caregivers. Unwaged labour, including slavery, indentured workers, debt peons, and homemakers are equally vital to our academic mandate.”²⁹

He further mentions that the GLHN, whose main pursuit is the ‘development of Global Labour History’, focuses on “... topics such as, for example, free and unfree labour, gender, migration, colonial labour, trade unions, or other issues of wider relevance...”³⁰ To him, the Global Labour History is “... a new approach to the study of work, workers and workers’ movements developed during the last two decades... this new field of historical research, which is encountering more and more interest in different parts of the world.”³¹ Thus Global Labor History with its new perspective is all embracing and more inclusive in its focus and approach.

Problems facing Global Labour History

Though the Global Labor History is emerging as an important branch of Global History or History, there are certain epistemological difficulties that needed to be realized and pondered over before historians embrace it. Firstly, most significantly, as Diego Olstein posits in his very thought-provoking work *Thinking History Globally*, the problem endures in adopting the four strategies of thinking history globally, i.e., in comparing, connecting, conceptualizing, and contextualizing the national narratives to global narratives.³² Secondly, the problems also persist in finding “...a shared purpose and common history”³³ among the historians of Global North and Global South, as the “questions of power and of the asymmetries between ‘the west and the rest’ can sometimes

²⁵ Peter Winn, *op.cit.*, p. 85

²⁶ Prasannan Parthasarathi, ‘Global Labor History: A Dialogue with Marcel van der Linden’, *International Labor and Working-Class History*, Fall 2012, No. 82, Fortieth Anniversary Issue (Fall 2012) p. 108.

²⁷ Peter Winn, *op. cit.*, p. 88.

²⁸ Cited in Prasannan Parthasarathi, *op. cit.*, p. 109 from Prasannan Parthasarathi and Giorgio Riello, "Introduction," in *The Spinning World: A Global History of Cotton Textiles, 1200-1850*, ed. Giorgio Riello

get lost in the focus on global circuits, processes, and connectivity.”³⁴ Furthermore, “...asymmetries of power and resources shape the global labor history that is written. Who gets to do “global history” and who gets to define the “global”? Global labor history may thus be more possible and more desirable in some places than others. It behooves us to ask, who is writing global history, and whose global history are we writing?”³⁵ Thirdly, more serious challenge to Global Labor History is present in the form of the development of research agenda given the vast diversity in working class formations and rise and growth of class culture in varied nations across the globe.³⁶ Fourthly, another difficulty persists in comprehending “the changing differential awareness of global connections and interconnected processes that form a causal chain.”³⁷ Fifthly, Global Labor History encounters daunting challenge in the necessity “...to rely on the vast empirical literature of the past national histories as well as on the old global history.”³⁸ It is argued that “Context matters, and without it we cannot construct or understand the globe.”³⁹

Sixthly, the study of the impact of democratic governments as also the non-democratic governments in different countries across the globe on the conditions of existence and the movements of the industrial workers constitutes yet another formidable challenge. The global labor historians writing on the history of labor in both the contexts with a comparative perspective encounter difficulties of comparison and analysis. Yet, the study of the conditions of existence and consciousness of the workers in mutually dissimilar contexts is significant for the future of labor and its survival.

The rise and rage of new technologies (for instance, the use of AI in varied activities) engender a trail of disruption on industrial laborers placing their occupations at threshold of jeopardy. To trace the rapid transformation with all its myriad

and Prasannan Parthasarathi (Oxford, 2009) 12.

²⁹ Marcel van der Linden, *op. cit.*, p. v.

³⁰ *Ibid.*

³¹ *Ibid*, p.vi.

³² Diego Olstein, *op. cit.*, pp.6-7.

³³ Peter Winn, *op. cit.*, p. 85.

³⁴ Dorothy Sue Cobble, *op. cit.*, p. 104.

manifestations and consequences taking place globally emerges as the most important challenge for a global labor historian.

Prospects for Global Labour History

Overcoming these challenges by the global labor historians culminates in the growth of a more robust global perspective shedding more enlightenment on the issues of global labor particularly in the context of expanding global economy and the changing political environments and the highs and lows in the responses of the working-class populations to them. It is perhaps important to note that Global Labor History is “...still a field “in construction,” whose contours and structures remain to be established...”⁴⁰ So to achieve this, it is important to promote the establishment of “...contact and cooperation between groups of labor historians in different regions, between labor historians and historians of related themes and between historians and social scientists.”⁴¹ Accordingly, the progress and consolidation of Global Labor History with its emphasis on exploring ‘interconnections’ is imperative “...to reorganise the way labor history is conceptualized, researched, and written around the world.”⁴² To really promote the agenda of the global labor history, historians aspiring to write on global labor issues “...must pose new questions or provide new answers to longstanding problems.”⁴³ Interestingly, global labor historians may attempt to disentangle the “...worker survival strategies, worker politics, and state actions...”⁴⁴. Here Prasannan Parthasarathi emphatically advances the idea that “Comparison is the means by which the divergent fates of laborers in different regions of the world may be comprehended and made sense of. Only with rigorous and systematic comparisons can new analytical insights be achieved and new categories be formed for understanding the pasts of laborers.”⁴⁵ He goes on to reiterate that “Comparison, therefore, creates the possibility for the more rigorous study of connections in global labor history”.⁴⁶

³⁵ *Ibid.*

³⁶ Peter Winn, *op. cit.*, p. 89

³⁷ *Ibid.*

³⁸ Dorothy Sue Cobble, *op. cit.*, p. 101.

³⁹ *Ibid.*

⁴⁰ Peter Winn, *op. cit.*, p. 89.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*, p. 90.

⁴² *Ibid.*

⁴³ Prasannan Parthasarathi, *op.cit.*, p. 109.

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 113.

⁴⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 109.

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 110.

As Peter Winn emphatically reiterates that “In a globalized world, we need a Global Labor History.”⁴⁷ Similarly Dorothy Sue Cobble, other prominent proponent of the Global Labor History, echoes thus: “I am thus a strong advocate of globalizing labor history and welcome the global turn in labor history as in other fields.”⁴⁸ Global Labor History, with ‘interconnections’ as its corner stone, is in the forefront of bringing the national narratives of the laborers to Global Canvas and thus is emerging as a significant and groundbreaking branch of the History. Global Labor History marks a fundamental departure from the ‘traditional labor history’ in that its concerns are different from earlier labor history. It includes all kinds of workers, who work “...in a variety of workplaces and modes of production and expands labor history’s temporal frame into earlier preindustrial eras.”⁴⁹ Here it is germane to note the inspirational articulation of Peter Winn. He writes thus: “Global Labor History will still be a task worth doing – even an enterprise worth embracing by younger labor historians around the world as their life’s work.”⁵⁰

Conclusion

Though the challenges to the progress of Global Labor History as an academic discipline are manifold and exist both at theoretical and methodological levels, its relevance as a fertile field of research on the issues of Global Labor remains undeniably significant. As the Capital goes global, so does the Labor. Hence the need for thinking Labor History globally becomes compelling.

Historians of Labor need to look beyond the national boundaries. As Diego Olstein maintains, transnational approach with emphasis on ‘comparing, connecting, conceptualizing, and contextualizing’ the issues of Labor is all what is needed to enrich and enlighten the Labor History globally. National histories are to be understood in global context. Thinking History or Labor History globally is imperative to understand History in its entirety.

⁴⁷ Peter Winn, *op.cit.*, p. 90.

⁴⁸ Dorothy Sue Cobble, *op.cit.*, p. 100.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*

⁵⁰ Peter Winn, *op.cit.*, p. 90.